

A CRITICAL REVIEW ON MASANUMASIKA GARBHINI PARICHARYA WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO FETAL DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

Pregnancy is a physiological yet delicate phase in a woman's life that requires meticulous care for ensuring the well-being of both mother and fetus. Ayurveda has elaborately described Garbhini Paricharya (antenatal care) with special emphasis on Masanumasika Paricharya — month-wise dietary and lifestyle regimen — to promote proper fetal growth and prevent complications during pregnancy and labour. Classical Ayurvedic texts such as Charaka Samhita, Sushruta Samhita, Ashtanga Hridaya and Kashyapa Samhita describe month-wise fetal development along with specific dietary recommendations to maintain doshic balance and ensure normal delivery. The present study aims to review classical references regarding Masanumasika Garbhini Paricharya and to elaborate the corresponding month-wise fetal development described in Ayurvedic literature. The prescribed regimen emphasizes Madhura rasa, Sheeta virya, Drava and Snigdha ahara in early months for proper cellular development, followed by Sneha and Ghrita preparations for structural maturation, and Basti therapy in later months for Vata regulation and facilitation of normal labour.

Ayurveda explains that maternal nutrition converts into Rasa Dhatu which nourishes three entities — mother, fetus, and future lactation (Stanya). Proper adherence to month-wise regimen results in healthy progeny possessing superior strength, complexion, immunity, and longevity. Thus, Masanumasika Paricharya represents a scientific and preventive obstetric approach that ensures safe motherhood and healthy offspring.

KEYWORDS: Garbhini Paricharya, Masanumasika Paricharya, Garbha Vriddhi, Apana Vayu, Prasava, Ayurveda.

INTRODUCTION

“To awaken people, it is the woman who must be awakened, once she is on the move, the family moves, the village moves, the nation moves.” - Pandit Javaharlal Nehru.

Above line indicates the importance of woman in our society. Woman is the backbone of family. She should always be cared as she is responsible for the unity and happiness of the family. Though woman is the important member of family, she is often neglected for her health. Hence this is the duty of family members, doctors and society to take care of her health. One of such moment when woman needs keen observation and proper health support is pregnancy. The joy of motherhood is the most precious moment in woman's life. Having a healthy baby is the dream of every woman but for having that joy she has to carry the developing fetus for more than nine months and at last have to suffer a painful step called as labour.

Ayurvedic classics have explained the importance of female as she is the most important part of human existence on this earth. A woman who has carried a fetus for nine months, who cared and followed all the precautions to keep the fetus safe has to pass through the stage of labour. This stage of delivering baby from the uterine environment to external world comprises a sequence of many changes occurring in both mother and the fetus.

Antenatal care is an important determinant of high maternal mortality rate. It is one of the basic components of maternal care on which the life of mothers and babies depends. Rates of Caesarean section in many countries have increased beyond the recommended level of 15%, almost doubling in the last decade, especially in high income areas such as Australia, France, Germany, Italy, North America and the United Kingdom of Great Britain and northern

Ireland (UK). Similar trends have also been documented in low-income countries such as Brazil, China and India.

CLASSICAL REVIEW

MASANUMASIK PARICHARYA OF GARBHINI OR RECOMMENDED DIET AND REGIMEN FOR VARIOUS MONTHS DURING PREGNANCY

First Month (Prathama Masa)

- The embryo is described as “**Kalala**” (semi-liquid mass).
- Charaka Samhita explains that the fertilized Shukra and Artava combine and remain in a semi-fluid stage.
- Nourishment through maternal Rasa begins.
- Hence, Sheeta, Madhura, Drava Ahara (mainly milk) is advised to support cellular formation.

Second Month (Dwitiya Masa)

- The embryo becomes “**Ghana**” (solid mass).
- Shape begins to differentiate into Pinda (mass), Arbuda (rounded), or Peshi (elongated).
- Organogenesis initiates in subtle form.
- Milk processed with Madhura Dravyas supports structural formation.

Third Month (Tritiya Masa)

- Formation of **five buds (Pancha Pindaka)** representing future limbs and head.
- Differentiation of Anga-Pratyanga begins.
- Fetal heartbeat perception is described indirectly via maternal cravings (Dauhrida).
- Milk with Madhu and Ghrita is recommended for proper tissue development.

Fourth Month (Chaturtha Masa)

- Stabilization of fetal organs.
- Heart (Hridaya) becomes prominent; consciousness becomes evident.
- Mother experiences specific desires (Dauhrida Avastha).
- Butter and protein-rich diet support muscular development.

Fifth Month (Panchama Masa)

- Development of **Mamsa and Rakta Dhatu predominance**.
- Increased fetal movements may be felt.

- Ghrita supports Dhatu Vriddhi and Ojas enhancement.

Sixth Month (Shashtha Masa)

- Development of **Bala and Varna**.
- Hair and fine body structures begin developing.
- Edema tendency may appear in mother.
- Gokshura-siddha Ghrita recommended for Mutravirechana and Vata-Pitta balance.

Seventh Month (Saptama Masa)

- Almost complete structural development.
- Viability stage described (though survival is delicate).
- Madhura Aushadhi Siddha Ghrita enhances fetal stability.

Eighth month (Ashtama Masa)

During 8th and 9th month of pregnancy basti is advised by acharyas for maintaining prakrut avastha of vata.

The regimen and diet prescribed, controls vata especially the Apan vayu. The functions of apan vayu are “Vata vinmutra-shukra-artava-garbh nishkramana aadikriyaha”. i.e. the expulsion of feces, urine, shukra, aartava and the delivery of fetus, hence to have normal delivery it is very important to maintain the vata.

Sushrut has advised Asthapana Basti with decoction of badar mixed with bala, atibala, shatpushpa, palal, milk, curds, mastu, oil, salt, madanphala, honey and ghruta and followed by Anuvasan basti with oils medicated with milk and decoction of madhur aushadhi dravyas. These would help in clearing the retained feces and vata-anuloman.

Ninth month (Navama Masa)

Charaka and Ashatang Sangraha have advised use of Anuvasana basti with oil prepared with the drugs of Madhur group or the same as used in eight month. Vaginal tampon of same oil should be given for lubrication of Garbha sthana and Garbhamarga.

Vagbhata has prescribed meat soup with cooked rice and fat or rice gruel mixed with good quality of fat. Anuvasana basti as advised in eight month and vaginal tampon of the same oil should be given. Daily bath with cold decoction of pounded leaves of drugs capable of

suppressing vata should be given. To the women having absence of unctuousness in the body Anuvasana Basti should always be given only after use of fat.

Harita opines that in ninth and tenth month different varieties of cereals should be used. Bhela says that Anuvasana Basti with Kadambamasha oil should be given, by use of this the accumulated feces goes in the lower passage, thus delivery of child becomes normal. After this basti rice gruel should be given.

Though Sushruta has not prescribed any specific dietetic regimen specifically for ninth month, however, in the regimen of eighth month after use of enema continuous use of unctuous gruels and meat soup of wild animals up to the period of delivery is advised. This indicates that Sushruta has advised use of unctuous gruel and meat soup of wild animals in ninth month also.

DISCUSSION

Benefits of monthly regimen

Describing the benefits of this dietetic regimen prescribed for the woman having normal development of fetus, Charak says that by this she remains healthy and delivers the child possessing good health, energy and strength, voice, compactness and much superior to other family members. Further Charak and Ashtang Sangrahaakar say that by the use of this regimen from first to ninth month her garbhdharini kukshi, sacral region, flanks and back become soft, vayu moves in its right path or direction i.e. feces, urine and placenta are excreted or expelled easily by their respective passage. Skin and nail becomes soft, women gains strength and complexion. She delivers normally at proper times. A desired, excellent, healthy child possessing all the qualities of long life can be delivered.

Sushruta has not described benefits separately, however, some of them mentioned are – fetus attains good growth, vayu moves in its right direction, woman becomes unctuous, strong and delivers the child easily without complications.

Diet consumed by garbhini converts into rasa, which serves three purposes in her body-nourishment of her own body, nourishment of fetus and nourishment of stanyashaya and formation of stanya. Hence the whole garbhini paricharya is beneficial not only to mother but also to fetus. It helps during the process of labour in order to overcome the complications which may occur during Prasava.

TABLE OF MASANUMASIK PATHYAS EXPLAINED IN DIFFERENT CLASSICS

Month	Charaka	Sushruta	Vagbhata	Harita
1 st month	Ksheeram Anupaskrutam	Madhur sheeta drava prayamaharam	Ksheeram upaskrutam- 12 days Ghruta + shaliparni & palash, anupana with swarna & rajat, madhur aushadhi	Navneet, Payas + Madhur & madhur rasa + yashtimadhu, parushaka, madhupushpa
2 nd month	Kshreeram + Madhuraushadha	Madhura Sheeta drava Prayamahaara	Kshreeram + Madhuraushadha	Kakoli + Madhura rasa
3 rd month	Kshreeram + Madhu + sarpi	Shashtika odan + Payas	Kshreeram + Madhu + sarpi	Kshira
4 th month	Ksheera + Navneeta	Payo navneeta samsruta jangala mamsa rasa	Kshreera + Aksha matra navneeta	Krutodana
5 th month	Ksheera sarpi	Ksheera sarpi samskruta	Kshreera sarpi	Ksheera
6 th month	Ksheera sarpi + Madhuroushadh siddham	Swadamshttra siddha sarpi	Ksheera sarpi + madhuruashadh siddham	Dadhi + Madhura rasa
7 th month	Ksheera sarpi + madhura oushadh siddham	Prushniparni siddha sarpi	Ksheera sarpi + Madhura oushadh siddham	Ghruta + khand
8 th month	Ksheera yavagu sarpisham	Badarodaka + bala + atibala+ shatpushpa + Tila + payadadhi / Mastu kashaya basti & sneha basti	Combined opinions of Charak and sushruta but eliminated shatpushpa, bala, atibala and advised basti	ghrutapoorak
9 th month	Anuvasan with madhur aushadhi siddha taila, pichu	----	Anuvasan with madhur aushadhi siddha taila, yoni pichu	Vividha anna

Our ayurvedic granthas have explained the month wise development of fetus and the effective result of developing fetus on the mother. Each month paricharya is designed to fulfill the requirement of both mother and fetus and to normalize the vitiated doshas in body which may create complications.

CONCLUSION

Masanumasika Garbhini Paricharya is a scientifically structured antenatal care protocol described in Ayurvedic classics. It provides month-wise dietary and therapeutic guidelines corresponding to fetal developmental milestones. The emphasis on Madhura, Snigdha, and Sheeta Ahara in early pregnancy supports cellular growth, while Sneha preparations in mid-pregnancy enhance Dhatu formation. Regulation of Apana Vayu in later months through Basti therapy facilitates normal labour.

This classical regimen demonstrates Ayurveda's profound understanding of embryology and maternal physiology. Proper implementation can reduce pregnancy-related complications and promote safe motherhood. Therefore, Masanumasika Paricharya should be considered a comprehensive and preventive antenatal care system contributing to healthy progeny and uncomplicated delivery.

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